

FINAL RESULTS FROM THE PASP PLUS FLIGHT EXPERIMENT

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ABSTRACT

Results from the PASP Plus flight experiment are given. PASP Plus was launched Aug. 3, 1994 into a 70 degree inclined elliptical orbit (2552x362km). The two main purposes of PASP Plus are to determine the inter-actions between the space plasma and biased arrays, and to compare the radiation degradation of several cell types (Si, GaAs, InP, amorphous Si, AlGaAs/GaAs, GaAs/CIS, and GaAs/GaSb). Both planar and concentrator technologies are represented. Data is available for 373 days when the controller stopped. Comparisons are made between predicted and actual flight data. The thermal performances of the modules are presented, as well as a flight-generated off-pointing curve for a concentrator module.

INTRODUCTION

The PASP Plus (Photovoltaic Array Space Power Plus Diagnostics) experiment is a flight experiment on the Air Force APEX Satellite (Advanced Photovoltaic and Electronics Experiments). There are two other small experiments on APEX, but PASP Plus uses most of the satellite power and data storage. The satellite was launched Aug. 3, 1994 and PASP Plus continued to operate until Aug. 11, 1995 when the controller stopped. This gave over one year of data. The satellite is in an elliptical orbit with an apogee of 2552 km and a perigee of 362 km. The inclination is 70 degrees. This orbit puts the spacecraft in a wide variety of plasma environments as well as gives it a fairly high radiation dose.

The two main purposes of the PASP Plus experiment are to determine the interactions between high voltage arrays and the space plasma and to determine the radiation damage characteristics of a variety of solar cells. Several of the individual modules are biased at various voltages up to plus or minus 500 volts at various times. Arcing rates and leakage currents are then measured. Radiation damage is determined by continuous monitoring of I-V data for all solar cell modules.

The purpose of this paper is to present the photovoltaic results from the 373 days when PASP Plus was active. Both electrical and thermal performances will be discussed. Comparisons with predicted performances based on AE8 and AP8 and the PASP Plus orbit will be discussed. Results from the first 80 days of operation were given at the last PVSC [1].

PASP PLUS DESCRIPTION

The PASP Plus experiment consists of twelve photovoltaic panels containing a total of sixteen separate cell modules. Two of the modules are concentrators and the rest are planar. Table I lists the different modules showing cell type, coverglass thickness, and number of cells. Note that not all the modules are biased during the experiment. The first eight modules are mounded on a deployed spacecraft panel, while the other eight modules are mounted on the top shelf of the APEX spacecraft. Both the deployed panel and the payload shelf are pointed towards the sun.

Two of the modules are samples of flexible arrays, Space Station and APSA. Both of these modules are mounted on the deployed panel over a corresponding opening in the panel. Hence both modules are open to the space environment both front and back. The APSA module has a thin layer of germanium applied to the thin film substrate for atomic oxygen protection.

In addition to the photovoltaic modules, PASP Plus has several diagnostic instruments to measure the space environment through which it is flying or help determine the plasma interactions with the biased arrays.

RESULTS

Three hours after the APEX spacecraft was launched, the PASP Plus experiment was turned on. The controller takes one I-V curve every 30 seconds, hence each module is sampled once every eight minutes. Taking into account eclipses and experiment

Table I. Pasp Plus Individual Cell Modules

<u>PASP Plus #</u>	<u>Cell Type</u>	<u>Array Type</u>	<u>Bias</u>	<u>Cells</u>	<u>Covers</u>
0	Silicon 2x4 cm	Planar	No	20	6 mils
1	Silicon 2x4 cm	Planar	Yes	20	6
2	Silicon 2x4 cm	Planar	Yes	60	6
3	Silicon 8x8 cm	Space Station	Yes	4	5
5	Silicon 2.6x5 cm	APSA	Yes	12	2.5
4	GaAs 4x4 cm	Planar	Yes	20	6
6	GaAs 4x4 cm	Planar	Yes	12	6
8	GaAs 4x4 cm WT	Planar	Yes	4	6
11	GaAs 4x4 cm	Planar	Yes	8	6
9	Amorphous Si 4x4cm	Planar	No	1	20
10	InP 2x2 cm	Planar	No	10	6
7	AlGaAs	Planar	No	20	24
12	GaAs/CIS 2x2 cm	Planar	No	9	2
13	GaAs/CIS 2x4 cm	Planar	No	3	2
14	GaAs	Cassegrainian	Yes	8	
15	GaAs/GaSb	Mini-Dome	Yes	12	

downtimes, we have over 854,000 I-V curves available for analysis. The data that follow obviously include only a small portion of the total data available.

The elliptical orbit that PASP Plus is flying in leads to a fair amount of sunlight reflected from the Earth that is incident on the solar cell modules. This albedo leads to a 5-6% variation in I_{sc} and P_{max} as discussed earlier [1]. We are able to tag those data points when the modules have a clear view of the sun without any albedo on the cell front surfaces. For this paper, we will use only the clear view data to eliminate the albedo variations. In all cases, the data have been corrected for the Earth-Sun distance and corrected to a base temperature. In an effort to reduce the possible errors in making temperature corrections, the data are corrected to the average temperature for I-V data during the first month of the flight. Hence each module is corrected to its own base temperature.

Silicon Cells

Figure 1 shows P_{max} for the life of the mission for module #0 (eight mill cells with 6 mil covers). In this figure, as well as all similar figures that follow, the solid line is the predicted module performance based on AE8 and AP8 and the PASP Plus orbital parameters. The broken curve consists of approximately 2500 to 3500 data points. Due to the nature of the 70 degree inclined orbit, clear view data is not available for long periods of time. The first available clear view data was 26 days after launch.

Fig. 1. P_{max} for module #0, silicon, corrected. to 32.9C. (Solid curve is predicted).

The first thing to notice about the performance of module #0 is that the degradation is much less than the predicted value. This is the case for all the silicon cell modules on PASP Plus. We have no final explanation for this other than perhaps AP8 is overestimating the proton fluences for the PASP Plus orbit. However, as will be seen later, the predicted curve is fairly close for GaAs.

Since we have no albedo free data until day 26, it is difficult to exactly obtain the initial data point. We have the average P_{max} for the first five hours of the flight but up to 6% albedo is included in this data point. In general, we fitted the predicted curve to a value on day 0 of about 2 to 3% under the measured value. For the silicon module #0, this leads to an initial value of about 2.87W. After 373 days it had degraded to about 2.38W or 82.8% of the initial value.

Figures 2 and 3 show Pmax for the life of the mission for the two flexible arrays, Space Station and APSA. Again, the predicted curves indicate more degradation than we actually measured on PASP Plus. Both of these modules are open to the space environment on the back and are lightly shielded. Hence there is more measured degradation than for silicon module #0. The Space Station module drops to 75.7% of its original value while APSA drops to 77.9%. It should be noted that these arrays are designed for lower radiation orbits.

Fig. 2. Pmax for module #3, Space Station, corrected to 50.7C. (Solid curve is predicted)

Fig. 3. Pmax for module #5, APSA, corrected to 52.7C. (Solid curve is predicted)

GaAs Cells

Figure 4 shows the Pmax data for the GaAs module #4. Notice the predicted curve is a much better fit to the measured data than for the silicon modules. This is so for all the GaAs modules on PASP Plus. This module degrades to 88.9% of its original Pmax value. The other GaAs modules show similar trends.

Fig. 4. Pmax for module #4, GaAs, corrected to 54.3C. (Solid curve is predicted)

There are three planar modules on PASP Plus which consist of GaAs based multi-junction cells. the AlGaAs/GaAs module #7 and the CLEFT GaAs/CIS modules #12 and 13. We only used the GaAs part in calculating the predicted degradation curves for these modules. Figures 5 and 6 show the Pmax data for modules #7 and #13.

Fig. 5. Pmax for module #7, AlGaAs/GaAs, corrected to 29.5C. (Solid curve is predicted)

Fig. 6. Pmax for module #13, GaAs/CIS, corrected to 43.3C. (Solid curve is predicted)

Degradation for the AlGaAs/GaAs module (Fig. 5) is almost exactly what is predicted, where the calculated curve is based on GaAs only. This module is heavily shielded with 24 mils of coverglass and degrades to only 94% of its original value. The CLEFT GaAs/CIS module (Fig. 6) has only 2 mil coverglasses and drops to 92% of its initial value. Note the predicted curve, again based on just GaAs, predicts much more degradation. The thin CLEFT cell, the low degradation of CIS, or an actual thicker coverglass could explain the difference.

Other Cells

Both InP and amorphous silicon modules were flown on PASP Plus. Figures 7 and 8 show the Pmax trends for these two modules. The InP cells had 6 mil covers like the silicon and GaAs modules and thus give us some direct comparisons in a proton dominated orbit. The InP module degraded to 94% of its original value which was less degradation than either GaAs or silicon (88.9% and 82.8%). Note that like the silicon modules, the predicted curve shows more degradation than the actual flight data. The amorphous silicon module (Fig.

8) shows an early drop in Pmax due to Stabler-Wronski, and then a leveling off. The drop in Pmax is to about 56% of the original value (0.129W). We have no predicted radiation damage curve for amorphous silicon. This cell has a 20 mil cover so minimal radiation damage is expected. This module showed some unique temperature dependencies. The fillfactor increased by about a third with increasing temperature (0 to 50C) leading to a positive Pmax temperature coefficient. This could be attributed to current mismatch in the triple junction amorphous cell.

Fig. 7. Pmax for module #10, InP, corrected to 44.6C. (Solid curve is predicted)

Fig. 8. Pmax for module 9, amorphous silicon, corrected to 38.1C.

Mini-Dome Concentrator

Figure 9 shows Pmax for the mini-dome fresnel lens concentrator module. Since the concentrator does not "see" albedo, we can use data from the entire mission, starting with day 0. The drop in Pmax is to 93.4% of its initial value with a fairly straight line with time. This is one of the least degraded modules on PASP Plus and shows the effect of a fairly thick secondary with mirror-

Fig. 9. Pmax for module 15, mini-dome concentrator, corrected to 48.3C.

like edges. This demonstrates one advantage of concentrators of having heavy shielding with minimal size covers. (Only the small cells need shielding.)

Figure 10 shows the effect of off-pointing the mini-dome concentrator module. The Isc drops to 90% of the peak value at an angle of about 3.5 degrees off normal. This compares favorably with a predicted value of 4 degrees.

Fig. 10. Measured off-pointing performance for mini-dome concentrator.

Temperature effects

Shortly after the start of the experiment, we noted the temperatures of all the modules were rising. This can be seen for three modules in Fig. 11. All six dates are during no-eclipse periods and each data point is the average for one complete orbit (231 data points 30 seconds apart). There is a rise of nearly 10 degrees and then a leveling off. We attribute this to darkening of the Z-93 thermal control paint on the PASP Plus shelf and deployed panel. This is confirmed by the lack of temperature rise on the three APEX solar cell panels which have no Z-93 paint.

Fig. 11 Temperature history of three PASP+ modules.

References

[1] H. Curtis, M. Piszczor, P. Severance, D. Guidice, & D. Olson, "Early Results from the PASP Plus Flight Experiment", First WCPEC, 1994, pp. 2169-2172.